

WHITE-ROT FUNGI OXIDATIVE COCKTAIL AS A TOOL FOR MODIFYING KRAFT LIGNIN INTO SUSTAINABLE CARBON FIBER PRECURSORS

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ABSTRACT

The growing demand for renewable materials has driven interest in lignin as a sustainable precursor for bio-based carbon fibers (CFs). However, its low molecular weight and limited thermal performance restrict its direct applicability. This study explores the enzymatic modification of Kraft lignin (KL) using an oxidative cocktail (LADEBIO-*Pys*) derived from *Pycnoporus sanguineus*, aiming to enhance its structural and processing characteristics for CF production. KL was treated with LADEBIO-*Pys* and *Trametes versicolor* laccase (KL-*Pys* and KL-*Tvs*, respectively). Both treatments significantly increased molecular weight (by over 150%) and polydispersity (over 110%), indicating efficient polymerization. FT-IR analysis showed intensified bands at 1700 and 1600 cm⁻¹, associated with carbonyl formation, C α oxidation, and the emergence of conjugated structures. ¹H NMR revealed reduced methoxyl protons and increased aliphatic hydroxyls, especially in KL-*Tvs*, suggesting extensive oxidation, demethylation, and radical coupling reactions (C–C and C–O), leading to a restructured lignin matrix. Thermal analysis indicated higher thermal instability in enzymatically treated lignins, with ~58% mass loss, reflecting side-chain degradation and structural rearrangements involving β -O-4 and β -1 linkages. Despite reduced stability, the treatments resulted in high-molecular-weight, reactive lignin structures with improved processability. Electrospinning experiments confirmed the benefits of enzymatic treatment. While untreated KL yielded brittle, discontinuous fibers, KL-*Pys* produced flexible, homogeneous mats. The addition of 1% polyethylene oxide (PEO) further improved fiber uniformity and mechanical integrity, yielding nanofibers with average diameters of ~ 0.20 μ m. The resulting material shows strong potential as a scalable, sustainable precursor for CFs and other high-performance biobased materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

Global demand for carbon fibers (CFs) has grown substantially over the past decade and a half [1–3]. From 42,900 metric tons in 2010, demand rose to 115,000 metric tons by 2023, an increase of approximately 168% [4]. This trend is projected to continue, reaching 280,300 metric tons by 2030, which would represent an additional 144% growth [4]. This expansion reflects CF's increasing relevance across a diverse range of sectors, including wind energy, automotive, pressure vessels, and construction [2,3]. As the market diversifies and scales up, there is a growing imperative to identify sustainable, cost-effective alternatives to petroleum-based precursors [2]. In this context, lignin, a widely available and chronically underutilized byproduct of the pulp and paper industry, has attracted increasing interest as a renewable precursor to produce lignin-based carbon fibers (LCFs) [1,2,5]. It is estimated that nature produces between 0.5 and 3.6 billion tons of lignin annually, with more than 70 million tons commercially generated, largely discarded as industrial waste [5]. Despite its abundance, the industrial application of lignin in CF production remains limited, constrained by its structural complexity and unresolved processing challenges [1,5].

The conversion of lignin into high-performance LCFs faces significant challenges due to its intrinsic structural complexity and the presence of contaminants such as ash, cellulosic residues, and inorganic salts, all of which can compromise fiber quality [6]. Unlike synthetic precursors such as PAN, lignin lacks a standardized conversion pathway [2]. Its transformation into spinnable fibers typically begins with compositional and rheological characterization, followed by targeted purification steps and spinning processes, such as melt, electrospinning, dry, or wet, chosen according to its physicochemical properties [1,5,7].

To improve LCFs' quality and mechanical performance, various strategies have been explored, including chemical, physical, and enzymatic treatments and their combinations. Among these, enzymatic approaches are particularly promising, leveraging oxidative enzymes such as laccases (Lac), lignin peroxidases (LiP), and manganese peroxidases (MnP). These enzymes catalyze the oxidation of phenolic and non-phenolic substructures in lignin, facilitating the cleavage of its resistant aromatic bonds [8]. As a result, they can promote increased molecular linearity, structural homogeneity, and hydroxyl group removal, yielding lignin with higher molecular weight and greater suitability as a PAN alternative in the production of high-performance CFs [9].

Despite these advantages, the industrial application of enzymes remains limited by factors such as low catalytic efficiency, narrow substrate specificity, and incomplete degradation [10,11]. In contrast to cellulose, which is efficiently hydrolyzed by well-optimized cellulolytic cocktails [12–14], lignin requires enzyme blends specifically tailored to address its heterogeneous and highly cross-linked structure. Effective cocktail design must consider the lignin source, pretreatment method, and desired end-products. While the synergistic interactions of cellulolytic enzymes are well-characterized and widely applied to enhance bioethanol yields from lignocellulosic biomass [15], lignin-directed enzymatic systems remain underdeveloped at an industrial scale.

This gap highlights a key biotechnological challenge: the development of enzymatic strategies that are not only effective but also economically and environmentally viable for lignin valorization. Within this framework, ligninolytic enzyme cocktails derived from white-rot fungi have emerged as a compelling solution. The basidiomycete *Pycnoporus sanguineus* has shown promise in producing key oxidative enzymes capable of targeting and cleaving lignin's aromatic framework. This study aimed to enhance Kraft lignin (KL) via enzymatic modification using a customized oxidative enzyme cocktail (LADEBIO-Pys) derived from *P. sanguineus*. The objective was to improve KL's polymerization behavior and processing characteristics, thereby reinforcing its potential as a sustainable precursor for CF production.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Production of the Enzymatic-Oxidative Cocktail from *P. sanguineus*

The oxidative enzymatic cocktail (LADEBIO-Pys) was produced by submerged cultivation of *P. sanguineus* (strain 2512, CCIBt/SP) in a bubble column reactor (Biostat B, B. Braun Biotech, USA) under fed-batch conditions for nine days. The culture medium was based on Mandels and Reese's [16]

formulation, optimized with a specific carbon-to-nitrogen ratio and supplemented with enzymatic inducers. The secretome was concentrated by tangential flow filtration (TFF), combining microfiltration (0.2 μm) and ultrafiltration (10 kDa), as previously described in our early study [17]. To evaluate the efficiency of the concentration process, three parameters were determined: the membrane rejection coefficient (ω) (equation 1); the volumetric concentration factor (F_c) (equation 2); and the overall process yield efficiency (R) (equation 3).

$$\omega (\%) = \left(1 - \frac{C_{UF}}{C_{PER}}\right) \times 100 \quad \text{Equation (1)}$$

$$F_c = \frac{V_{Eb}}{V_{UF}} \quad \text{Equation (2)}$$

$$R (\%) = (F_c)^{(\omega-1)} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation (3)}$$

Where C_{UF} is the enzymatic concentration in the ultrafiltration retentate (U/L); C_{PER} is the residual enzymatic concentration in the permeate (U/L); V_{Eb} is the initial volume of crude extract (L); V_{UF} is the final volume after 10 kDa ultrafiltration (L).

2.2 Enzymatic Activity Assays and Protein Quantification

Lac, MnP, and LiP activities were measured by the oxidation of ABTS (420 nm), phenol red (610 nm), and veratryl alcohol (310 nm), respectively, following established protocols, Wolfenden and Willson and Tien and Kirk [18–20]. Xylanase (XyL), β -glucosidase (β -G), avicelase (AV), FPase (FP), and CMCase (CMC) were quantified according to Eveleigh et al.[21]. One enzymatic unit (U) corresponds to the oxidation of 1 μmol of substrate per minute. Total protein (PTN) content was determined using the Bradford method with BSA as a standard (595 nm) [22]. The enzymatic cocktail was evaluated by SDS-PAGE to assess its protein diversity, using 12–15% denaturing polyacrylamide gels under standard Laemmli [23] conditions. Protein visualization was performed using Coomassie Brilliant Blue staining, and molecular weight markers (Pierce, Thermo Scientific) were used for reference [24].

2.3 Enzymatic Oxidation of KL

Enzymatic modification was performed in a reaction medium containing 10 g/L of KL, an enzyme load of 30 mg/g (based on total protein), using either the LADEBIO-*Pys* cocktail or a commercial laccase from *Trametes versicolor* (> 0.5 U/mg). The medium also included ABTS (25 mg/g), H_2O_2 (10 mg/g), and MnSO_4 (10 mg/g), in 2 mmol/L sodium phosphate buffer (pH 5.0). Reactions were performed in 250 mL bioreactors at 40 °C, 400 rpm for 48 h with continuous air flow (2 L/min). After treatment, the enzymes were thermally inactivated (80 °C, 10 min), washed three times with deionized water, centrifuged (25,000 g, 15 min), and oven-dried at 60 °C for 48 h.

2.4 Physicochemical Characterization of Modified Lignin

Molecular weight distribution was determined by Advanced Polymer Chromatography (APC) using DMSO/LiBr (0.5% w/v) as solvent at 90 °C and a 0.5 mL/min flow rate [25]. Calibration was performed with polystyrene sulfonate standards. Thermal stability was assessed using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) on a Q500 analyzer under nitrogen (30 mL/min), heating samples from 30 °C to 800 °C at 10 °C/min. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to determine glass transition temperature (T_g), employing a heating protocol from 50 °C to 200 °C (20 °C/min), followed by controlled cooling and second heating (10 °C/min), under nitrogen flow (50 mL/min). Structural analysis by FT-IR was performed with KBr pellets (2 mg lignin + 200 mg KBr, pressed at 10 MPa), scanning from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} . Oxidation degree (Θ) was determined by calculating the absorbance ratio between the characteristic oxidation bands and the reference band at 1510–1513 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to aromatic

skeletal vibrations and remains largely unaffected by oxidative reactions, thus serving as an internal standard [26]. ¹H NMR spectra were acquired after dissolving 20 mg of dried lignin in 600 μ L DMSO- d_6 with 22 μ L pentafluorobenzaldehyde (PFB) as internal standard. Analyses were performed at 25 $^{\circ}$ C, using the *zgpr* pulse sequence with 128 scans and 10 s relaxation delay. Peaks were referenced to PFB (10.28 ppm) and DMSO- d_6 (2.50 ppm) [27].

2.5 Electrospinning and Morphological Analysis

Electrospinning was performed using a custom-built setup with a 30 kV power source, syringe pump, and metallic collector. The voltage was fixed at 16 kV, with a 0.05 mL/min flow rate, 8.0 cm needle-to-collector distance, and stainless-steel 18G 1/2 needle. Two formulations were evaluated: KL enzymatically treated with the LADEBIO-*Pys* cocktail alone and blended with 1% (w/w) polyethylene oxide (PEO). The solutions were prepared at a 2:3 (w/w) solid-to-solvent ratio in DMF: acetone (9:1, w/w) [28,29]. Resulting lignin fibers were characterized by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) using a Hitachi TM3030Plus at 15 kV, with magnifications from 200 \times to 6000 \times . Samples were analyzed, and average fiber diameters (θ) were calculated using ImageJ software.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Obtention and Characterization of the LADEBIO-*Pys* Cocktail

Figure 1 presents the enzymatic activities of Lac, LiP, MnP, and PTN following TFF and concentration using a hollow fiber system. As shown, sequential microfiltration and ultrafiltration steps led to the recovery of four enzymatic cocktails highly enriched in ligninolytic enzymes. Lac and MnP activities reached their maximum values in the third batch, while LiP activity peaked in the first. This variation reflects the dynamics of enzyme secretion during cultivation and recovery.

Figure 1: Batch recovery and tangential flow filtration (TFF) performance of the oxidative enzymatic cocktail LADEBIO-*Pys* from *P. sanguineus*. (a) Enzyme recovery in batch mode for Lac, LiP, MnP, and PTN (b) TFF yield (R) and membrane rejection coefficient (ω) for SB1 and FB2–FB4. SB1: first single batch; FB2–FB4: fed-batch recoveries performed after alimentation on the seventh, eighth, and ninth days, respectively.

Ultrafiltration using a hollow fiber system with a 10 kDa molecular weight cut-off resulted in substantial increases in enzymatic activity ($>100\%$, Fig. 1b), primarily due to the removal of low-molecular-weight compounds and water. This led to volumetric concentration and enrichment of active enzymes. The membrane rejection coefficients (ω) remained consistently high for all enzymes (89.81%–98.78%, Fig. 1b), indicating strong selectivity and process efficiency, with LiP exhibiting the highest retention. These results reinforce the robustness of the TFF system (Fig. 1) in concentrating enzymatic cocktails while minimizing losses and denaturation. Kinetic monitoring revealed an increasing trend in

R and ω values post-filtration, likely due to progressive membrane fouling caused by pigment accumulation, especially cinabarin, a red phenoxazinone compound secreted in large amounts by *P. sanguineus* (Fig. 2b). This fouling may contribute to enhanced enzyme retention by forming a secondary filtration layer, as visually supported by the crude extract's color profile (Fig. 2a-c). These values position *P. sanguineus* as a potent producer of ligninolytic enzymes, corroborated by prior studies [24,30,31].

The enzymatic profile of the LADEBIO-Pys cocktail, produced by *P. sanguineus*, reflects the cumulative outcome of four sequential batches obtained through TFF and reveals a remarkable co-secretion of lignin-modifying enzymes (LMEs) alongside cellulolytic hydrolases, as illustrated in Figure 2. Post-filtration activity levels for Lac, LiP, and MnP reached 6.8×10^5 , 3.0×10^4 , and 1.5×10^3 U/L, respectively, reflecting the strain's strong oxidative capacity. Concomitantly, substantial activities of β -G, Xyl, AV, FP, and CMC were also detected, with β -G and CMC activities ranging from 4 to 5,000 U/L, indicating a robust polysaccharide-degrading potential (Fig.2e).

Figure 2: Recovery and partial characterization of the oxidative enzymatic cocktail LADEBIO-Pys from *P. sanguineus*. (a) Hollow fiber filtration system used for TFF and concentration; (b) membrane segment showing crude extract pigmentation; (c) LADEBIO-Pys after ultrafiltration; (d) protein profile by SDS-PAGE (MW marker, 1x and 5x dilutions); (e) enzymatic activity profile of the lignocellulolytic complex.

The observed enzymatic profile is consistent with prior reports: Pereira Scarpa et al. [32] identified a similar range of enzymes, including LMEs and glycoside hydrolases, during solid-state fermentation; Azmi, Jalil, and Kalil [33] reported elevated FP, CMC, and exoglucanase activities under α -cellulose fermentation; and Sahaid Kalil et al. [34] demonstrated peak cellulase production within 48 h of cultivation. The coexistence of oxidative and hydrolytic activities in a single fungal secretome not only underscores the metabolic flexibility of *P. sanguineus* but also reinforces its biotechnological relevance for integrated biorefinery strategies focused on the enzymatic valorization of lignocellulosic biomass into high-value compounds such as platform chemicals and functional biomaterials.

3.2 Molecular Characterization of Enzymatically Modified KL

Figure 3 shows that the enzymatic treatments of KL using either *T. versicolor* commercial laccase (KL-Tvs) or the LADEBIO-Pys cocktail (KL-Pys), both in the presence of ABTS mediator, resulted in a significant increase in molecular weight (Mw) and polydispersity index (PDI) after 48 hours of reaction, when compared to the untreated control (KL).

Mw values rose by 157% (Lac-Tv) and 152% (LADEBIO-Pys), while PDI increased by 110% and 115%, respectively. These findings align with those reported by Ibarra et al. [35], who observed a 1.8-fold Mw increase with bacterial laccase SiLA (SiLA-KL1) and a 1.7-fold increase with fungal laccase MtL (MtL-KL1), accompanied by similar increases in PDI. According to Areskog et al. [36], such

outcomes are attributed to the non-selective radical–radical coupling reactions triggered by the oxidation of terminal phenolic groups in lignin, wherein free radicals spontaneously couple without spatial or steric control (Fig. 3b). This leads to broad molecular weight distributions, thereby increasing polydispersity.

Figure 3: Enzymatic modification of Kraft lignin (KL). (a) GPC analysis and (b) Oxidation pathways: (I) LADEBIO-*Pys* system promotes radical formation and synergistic polymerization; (II) LacTv-ABTS acts via redox cycling.

Despite the longer reaction time applied in our study (48 h), the results suggest that the LADEBIO-*Pys* system efficiently promotes structural remodeling of lignin not only through oxidative polymerization, but also via cleavage of key interunit linkages such as β -O-4, β -5, β - β , 4-O-5, and 5-5, as proposed by Vignali et al. [37] and Zhu et al. [36] (Fig. 3b). Our findings support the literature postulate that polymerization is initiated by single-electron abstraction from the phenylpropanoid moieties of lignin by either LacTv or the LADEBIO-*Pys*/ABTS system, generating phenoxy radicals that activate the lignin surface [38,39]. Given the extended π -conjugation systems in lignin, the unpaired electron is delocalized to more stable resonance structures. Phenolic units are oxidized to phenoxy radicals, whereas non-phenolic regions form β -aryl and benzylic radicals. These species act as reactive intermediates that undergo radical–radical coupling, involving either lignin–lignin or lignin–mediator linkages. This process results in covalent polymer growth and an overall increase in Mw, as illustrated in Figure 3, thus demonstrating the dual oxidative and structural modification capabilities of the enzymatic systems evaluated [38,39].

3.3 Structural Modifications Detected by FT-IR and ¹H NMR

FT-IR spectroscopic analysis (Figure 4a-b) indicated that, although the aromatic scaffold of KL remained largely conserved following enzymatic oxidation, substantial alterations were observed in specific functional groups, notably in the ν (OH), ν (COOH), ν (C=O), and ν (OCH₃) absorption regions. The broad ν (OH) stretching band (3300–3600 cm⁻¹), present across all spectra, showed a marked attenuation at approximately 3441 cm⁻¹ in the KL-Tvs sample.

This reduction suggests a significant depletion of –OH, likely attributable to the pronounced oxidative potential of *T. versicolor* laccase, especially when operating within the ABTS-mediated redox system [40]. Conversely, the KL-*Pys* sample exhibited a comparatively moderate decrease in this band, possibly resulting from simultaneous oxidative cleavage and regeneration of hydroxyl functionalities at the side chains, a phenomenon that may be enhanced by the synergistic action of accessory oxidoreductases present in the LADEBIO-*Pys* enzymatic cocktail. Additionally, both enzymatically treated samples displayed a discernible decline in the ν (C–H) stretching bands (2800–2900 cm⁻¹), corresponding to aliphatic methylene and methyl groups (Fig. 4b) [41]. This behavior is indicative of partial demethylation and demethoxylation processes, in agreement with previously reported depolymerization and structural simplification mechanisms for lignin matrices subjected to oxidative biocatalysis [42].

Figure 4: Structural and thermal characterization of Kraft lignin (KL) before and after enzymatic treatment with LADEBIO-Pys and *T. versicolor* laccases. (a) FTIR spectra acquired via KBr pellet method; (b) Quantitative comparison of main functional group peaks (Θ); (c) ¹H NMR spectra; (d) TGA and DTA thermograms; (e) DSC curves.

More notably, oxidative effects were evident in the carbonyl domain: normalized intensities at $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ in conjugated systems) and $\sim 1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (non-conjugated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$) increased by up to 2.88-fold and 1.71-fold, respectively, in both treatments (Figure 4b). These spectral changes are consistent with oxidative cleavage of $\text{C}\alpha\text{-OH}$ groups, quinone formation, and disruption of interunit linkages such as $\beta\text{-O-4}$, $\alpha\text{-O-4}$, and 4-O-5 , as proposed by Gouveia *et al.* [43]. Concurrent reductions at 1464, 1428, and 1368 cm^{-1} support partial loss of -OCH_3 and aliphatic -OH moieties, indicating demethylation reactions [42]. Visual darkening of lignin samples (data not shown) corroborates the formation of extended π -conjugated systems.

¹H NMR analysis (Fig. 4c) revealed marked structural changes across KL, KL-Pys, and KL-Tvs, particularly in regions assigned to aromatic protons (Ar-H, 8.6–6.28 ppm), methoxyl groups (-OCH_3 , 4.2–3.1 ppm), aromatic hydroxyls (Ar-OH, 2.5–2.25 ppm), aliphatic hydroxyls (Al-OH, 2.25–2.0 ppm), and aliphatic acetates (-O-COCH_3 , ~ 2.23 ppm). The signal reduction in Ar-OH and Al-OH was more pronounced in KL-Tvs, indicating a greater oxidative impact. A significant decrease in the -OCH_3 region, particularly in KL-Tvs, suggests extensive demethylation, corroborated by FT-IR analysis. Simultaneously, the increase in -O-COCH_3 signals indicates the formation of new Al-OH groups through oxidative cleavage and rearrangement. The marked reductions in Ar-H signals support the occurrence of oxidative coupling reactions (C-C and C-O-C), leading to aromatic ring condensation. Collectively, these transformations point to complex biochemical mechanisms, including direct oxidation of phenolic units, demethylation of -OCH_3 groups, formation of quinones and carbonyl functionalities (-CHO , -CO-), and radical-mediated polymerization.

3.4 Thermal Properties and Stability of Modified Lignin

The thermal analysis (TGA-DTA and DSC) of enzymatically treated KL provides critical insights

into the structural transformations as shown in Figure 4d-e and Table 1, both KL-*Pys* and KL-*Tvs* exhibited a decrease in the onset ($T_{d,onset}$) and maximum degradation temperatures ($T_{d,max}$), accompanied by a higher total mass loss (~58%) compared to the untreated control (KL, 64.1%).

	$T_{d,onset}$ (°C)	$T_{d,max}$ (°C)	Mass loss (%)	T_g (°C)	T_c (°C)
KL	236	389	64.10	154.95	
KL-<i>Tvs</i>	226	374	57.88	164.78	n.d.
KL-<i>Pys</i>	229	379	57.63	163.65	

Table 1: Thermal parameters of native and enzymatically modified KL samples.

This reduction in thermal stability suggests that enzymatic oxidation, despite leading to polymerization and molecular weight increase as evidenced by GPC (Fig. 3), also introduces thermolabile functional groups such as C=O, COOH, and conjugated systems, as confirmed by FT-IR and ¹H-NMR (Fig. 4c). These functionalities weaken the internal cohesion of the lignin matrix, facilitating early-stage degradation. The DTG profiles (Fig. 4e) further substantiate this interpretation, indicating a shift in the degradation of propanoid side chains and aryl-ether bonds to lower temperature ranges. This behavior likely stems from the oxidative cleavage of interunit linkages (β -O-4, β -5), followed by cross-linking and radical coupling reactions, as discussed in the mechanistic analysis (Fig. 2b), resulting in a KL structure that is simultaneously more condensed yet more chemically reactive and thermally sensitive.

DSC analysis (Fig. 4e) revealed an approximately 6.5 % increase in T_g for both KL-*Pys* and KL-*Tvs*, compared to KL, indicating restricted polymer chain mobility due to oxidative crosslinking. Despite the reduced thermal stability observed by TGA, this elevation in T_g suggests the formation of rigid, high-molecular-weight domains (e.g., β -1, β - β), which counterbalance the presence of low-molecular-weight fragments introduced during oxidation. This dual thermal behavior aligns with FT-IR and ¹H-NMR evidence of demethoxylation, C=O incorporation, and radical-induced condensation. Interestingly, KL-*Pys* exhibited a T_g comparable to KL-*Tvs*, despite showing milder spectroscopic changes, indicating that the multienzymatic nature of the LADEBIO-*Pys* cocktail (rich in Lac, LiP, and MnP) may promote broader oxidative diversification than a single purified laccase.

Notably, no crystallization temperature (T_c) was detected in any sample. Although enzymatic oxidation modifies lignin's macromolecular structure, it does not induce long-range order or crystallinity, consistent with the amorphous nature of lignin. These thermal features, summarized in Table 1, reinforce those enzymatic treatments, particularly with broad-spectrum oxidative cocktails, enhance lignin's rigidity and thermal behavior without altering its fundamental amorphous character, improving its suitability for FC precursor applications.

3.5 Electrospinning Performance and Mat Morphology

Electrospinning assays demonstrated that oxidative enzymatic modification of KL using the LADEBIO-*Pys* cocktail significantly enhanced its ability to form lignin-based FC precursors. As shown in Figure 5a–b, native KL, either with or without the addition of polyethylene oxide (PEO), resulted in electrospinning, producing non-fibrous, brittle mats composed of aggregated lignin droplets. These outcomes underscore the structural limitations of unmodified KL for direct fiber formation via electrospinning, the first step in the CF production chain. In contrast, KL-*Pys* generated continuous lignin fibers (Fig. 5c), indicating that oxidative modifications conferred by the LADEBIO-*Pys* cocktail effectively adjusted the physicochemical properties of KL, enabling filament formation. The inclusion of PEO (Fig. 5d), used here as a rheological aid rather than a structural matrix, further improved the quality and cohesion of the lignin fiber mats. However, SEM analysis revealed bead formation in KL-*Pys*:PEO samples, indicating the need for further optimization of the lignin-to-PEO ratio to minimize defects and promote uniformity.

Figure 5: Electrospinning performance of Kraft lignin (KL) samples. (a–b) optical and SEM images of untreated KL with and without PEO (c) 100 % KL-*Pys*; (d) 99% KL-*Pys*:1 % PEO; (e–f) Diameter distribution histograms for KL-*Pys* and KL-*Pys*:PEO fibers, respectively

Diameter distribution histograms (Fig. 5e–f) confirmed a significant reduction in average fiber diameter from 0.99 μm in KL-*Pys* to 0.20 μm in KL-*Pys*:PEO along with a decrease in the coefficient of variation (6.4% to 4.2%), suggesting improved control over lignin fiber deposition when PEO is used as a processing aid. These findings agree with previous reports that emphasize the importance of polymer additives in modulating solution viscosity and electrospinning behavior, particularly for lignin-rich systems [38].

3.6 Technological Potential of LADEBIO-*Pys*

The oxidative enzymatic cocktail LADEBIO-*Pys*, obtained from *P. sanguineus* via submerged fermentation and concentrated using single TFF, stands out as a low-cost, high-performance biocatalyst for KL modification. With high activities of Lac, LiP, and MnP along with relevant cellulolytic enzymes, this ultrafiltrate enabled effective oxidative depolymerization and repolymerization. Together, the results confirm that the enzymatic oxidative modification of KL promotes the formation of continuous lignin nanofibers. The improvements in spinnability are attributed to structural transformations such as partial depolymerization, oxidative repolymerization, and the introduction of oxygenated functionalities, reflected in increased M_w , higher T_g , and new IR-active groups positioning KL-*Pys* as a promising renewable precursor for FC production.

Notably, the LADEBIO-*Pys* system combines catalytic efficiency with operational simplicity; it circumvents the need for costly and time-consuming downstream purification. Given that downstream processing is often cited as a major economic bottleneck in enzyme production, the ability to obtain a crude yet highly active oxidative cocktail that performs on par with purified enzymes is of considerable industrial relevance. The synergistic interplay among its enzymes enables not only oxidative cleavage but also controlled radical polymerization, yielding structurally reorganized lignin with enhanced thermal behavior and processability. As Perna et al. [38] emphasize, such enzyme synergy is crucial for tailoring polymer architectures, and our results confirm this principle even in non-purified enzyme systems.

Despite its demonstrated potential, oxidative enzymatic cocktails like LADEBIO-*Pys* remain underdeveloped and largely unavailable in the commercial market. This scarcity is especially notable considering increasing interest in lignin valorization and the rise of "Lignin-First" strategies, which prioritize early-stage lignin processing in biorefinery models. The limited availability of such catalytic systems hampers innovation in lignin-derived materials, not only for FC production, but also for high-performance composites, adhesives, supercapacitors, and fine chemicals. Therefore, expanding the development, accessibility, and application of multienzymatic oxidative systems represents a critical

step toward democratizing lignin bioconversion technologies, reducing processing costs, and enabling sustainable pathways for the transformation of lignin into high-value biomaterials.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this study demonstrate that the oxidative enzymatic cocktail LADEBIO-Pys is a powerful and scalable tool for the structural modification of KL. By promoting efficient polymerization and oxidation, the system significantly enhanced the molecular weight, thermal stability, and chemical reactivity of KL. When combined with PEO, the enzymatically modified lignin yielded electrospun mats with superior morphological and structural integrity. Their nanofibrous architecture and improved uniformity make them strong candidates for FC precursors. Altogether, LADEBIO-Pys offers a promising route for lignin valorization within integrated and sustainable biorefinery platforms.

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